

COMPETENCES FOR ALL: RECOGNIZING AND DEVELOPING COMPETENCES OF YOUNG PEOPLE WITH FEWER OPPORTUNITIES

Hakan Uşaklı¹

Assoc. Prof. Dr., Sinop University, Education Faculty, Turkey

Abstract

This qualitative study clarifies opinion of 32 European volunteer youth leaders on concepts of competence, fewer opportunities and enlargement strategies on competence of fewer opportunities. Leaders underline main competencies as follows: tongue, languages, mathematical, digital, learning, social, entrepreneurship, cultural. Key competences are those which all individuals need for personal fulfillment and development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employment (Figel, 2007). The key competences are all considered equally important, because each of them can contribute to a successful life in a knowledge society. According to leader, fewer opportunities mean; obstacles can prevent such young people from having access to education, to mobility, to participation. All leaders agree with the non-formal education which is base for development of competence of fewer opportunities. Non-formal education may be one of them, especially – but not solely – for young people with fewer opportunities (Strenner, 2006). Leaders have lack of knowledge on dimension of non-formal learning for fewer opportunities. Future studies should be conduct on approved techniques and strategies of development of competence of fewer opportunities young people. Especially experimental researchers are very important. European youth volunteer organizations such as SALTO should widen programs all around the Europe. Today's world reality makes volunteer non-formal education obligatory.

Keywords: competence, fewer opportunity, strategies for development of competencies

¹ Correspondence: email husakli@yahoo.com, husakli@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Between 5 and 11 May 2011 32 European volunteer youth leaders met in Seamen's House (Habour) Hotel in Antwerp Belgium. In this six days meeting they expressed ideas on what competence is, what is fewer opportunity and what are the techniques and strategies of development of competence in fewer opportunities. Hot wars around the world especially Iraq and Syria wars force people immigrate. There is news about immigration via non formal ways especially to de European countries. This new population of Europe made governments new precautions. There are organizations such as SALTO-YOUTH has been arranging educational and training activities for young and adults especially volunteer leaders.

Competences for all! Recognizing competences of young people with fewer opportunities is one of SALTO educational meeting occur in 5-11 May 2011. Specialists from 12 different European countries participated in this educational meeting. Volunteer youth leaders expressed their ideas on competences, fewer opportunities and development of competencies in fewer opportunities. This encounter of specialist made insight on competence and fewer opportunity concepts.

Youth work helps young people to develop skills and competences in many areas; but it also helps them to strengthen their networks, to change their behavior and to build positive relationships (EC, 2015: 12). Competences acquired by the participants during the training included skills to run inclusive, dynamic, engaging and creative workshops and sessions for children and youth, and social skills such as communicating in different environments, understanding different viewpoints, and cultural expression and awareness (EC, 2015: 127)

Human resource development (HRD) practitioners and educators use the word competence in different ways. In general terms, competences are 'written descriptions of measurable work habits and personal skills used to achieve a work objective' (Green, 1999; Burke, 1989). Some scholars see competence as a combination of knowledge, skills and behavior used to improve performance; or as the state or quality of being adequately or well qualified, having the ability to perform a specific role (Tuxworth, 1989; Boyatzis, 1982). For the lifelong learning concept in the EU, a competence is a complex array of knowledge, skills and attitudes that is verified during an activity to attain a certain goal (EC, 2015: 4).

Out of the eight key competences identified by the European Commission (2015), there is one that stands out: sense of entrepreneurship and initiative. This competence refers to the ability to put ideas into action, particularly relevant in the field of employability. It is characterized by a sense of initiative, creativity, independence and

innovation in personal and social life and work. It requires motivation and determination in achieving goals. It can be broken down into its components: knowledge, skills and attitudes (EC, 2015: 132).

These dimensions reflect developmental tasks related to academic achievement, social competence, and conduct important at both age levels in U.S. society, and the additional tasks of romantic and job competence in adolescence. As hypothesized, rule-breaking versus rule-hiding conduct showed strong continuity over time, while academic achievement and social competence showed moderate continuity.

2. Problem Statement

2.1 Defining Competence

"Competence" has had varied meanings in psychology, ranging from motivational processes to behavioral effectiveness in the tasks of living (Ford, 1985; Garmezy & Masten, 1991; Waters & Sroufe, 1983). Competence belongs to a family of constructs that includes the ego (Block & Block, 1980- Freud, 1923/1960; Hartmann, 1939/1958; Loevinger, 1976), effectance and self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977; Harter, 1985a; White, 1959), intelligence and intelligent behavior (Charlesworth, 1991; Sternberg, 1985; Wechsler, 1958), premorbid competence (Garmezy, 1970; Phillips, 1968; Zigler & Glick, 1986), and developmental tasks (Erikson, 1963; Havighurst, 1972; Sroufe, 1979). Each of these constructs represents attempts to explain or describe the effectiveness of adaptation in the environment, although they vary in whether they focus on internal structures, internal processes, or observed behavior.

3. Key Competences

Competences are defined here as a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes appropriate to the context. Key competences are those which all individuals need for personal fulfillment and development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employment.

The Reference Framework sets out eight key competences:

1. Communication in the mother tongue;
2. Communication in foreign languages;
3. Mathematical competence and basic competences in science and technology;
4. Digital competence;
5. Learning to learn;
6. Social and civic competences;

7. Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship; and
8. Cultural awareness and expression. (EU, 2006: 13; Pacheco, et al 2009: 60; Alban & Geudens, 2008: 2012: 83; Schroeder, Hendriks & Bergstein., 2012: 19; Schild & Hebel, 2006: 9).

Key competence is used to designate competencies that enable individuals to participate effectively in multiple contexts or social fields and that contribute to an overall successful life for individuals and to a well-functioning society (i.e. lead to important and valued individual and social outcomes)." (Rychen, 2004 p. 22).

The Eurydice report on key competencies (Eurydice, 2002) reviews the literature on the topic key competencies and suggests two criteria to decide about key competencies: *"The first criterion for selection is that key competencies must be potentially beneficial to all members of society. They must be relevant to the whole of the population, irrespective of gender, class, race, culture, family background or mother tongue. Secondly, they must comply with the ethical, economic and cultural values and conventions of the society concerned"* (Eurydice, 2002, p. 14).

Eurydice also concludes about key competencies: *"The main conclusion to be drawn from the large number of contributions to this search for a definition is that there is no universal definition of the notion of 'key competence'. Despite their differing conceptualisation and interpretation of the term in question, the majority of experts seem to agree that for a competence to deserve attributes such as 'key', 'core', 'essential' or 'basic', it must be necessary and beneficial to any individual and to society as a whole. It must enable an individual to successfully integrate into a number of social networks while remaining independent and personally effective in familiar as well as new and unpredictable settings. Finally, since all settings are subject to change, a key competence must enable people to constantly update their knowledge and skills in order to keep abreast of fresh developments"* (Eurydice, 2002, p. 14).

Key competences can therefore be seen as the competences required for an individual well-being in that society. There are three major factors that have been highlighted: first, the knowledge economy – a competences that enables you to get a job, second, lifelong learning – the ability to continue to update your skills in a rapidly changing job market and third, social cohesion – that people have the social skills necessary for society to function in a democratic manner and in a culturally diverse environment. Learning to learn has been argued to be a transversal competence that is necessary for wellbeing in Europe and in particular is highly relevant for developing and updating job related skills (Hoskins & Fredriksson, 2008: 13).

Competences are defined here as a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes appropriate to the context. Key competences are those which all individuals

need for personal fulfillment and development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employment.

The key competences are all considered equally important, because each of them can contribute to a successful life in a knowledge society. Many of the competences overlap and interlock: aspects essential to one domain will support competence in another. Competence in the fundamental basic skills of language, literacy, numeracy and in information and communication technologies (ICT) is an essential foundation for learning, and learning to learn supports all learning activities. There are a number of themes that are applied throughout the Reference Framework: critical thinking, creativity, initiative, problem-solving, risk assessment, decision-taking, and constructive management of feelings play a role in all eight key competences.

Communication in the mother tongue (1) Communication in the mother tongue is the ability to express and interpret concepts, thoughts, feelings, facts and opinions in both oral and written form (listening, speaking, reading and writing), and to interact linguistically in an appropriate and creative way in a full range of societal and cultural contexts; in education and training, work, home and leisure (Figel, 2007).

Communication in foreign languages (2) Communication in foreign languages broadly shares the main skill dimensions of communication in the mother tongue: it is based on the ability to understand, express and interpret concepts, thoughts, feelings, facts and opinions in both oral and written form (listening, speaking, reading and writing) in an appropriate range of societal and cultural contexts (in education and training, work, home and leisure) according to one's wants or needs. Communication in foreign languages also calls for skills such as mediation and intercultural understanding. An individual's level of proficiency will vary between the four dimensions (listening, speaking, reading and writing) and between the different languages, and according to that individual's social and cultural background, environment, needs and/or interests (Figel, 2007).

Mathematical competence and basic competences in science and technology
Mathematical competence is the ability to develop and apply mathematical thinking in order to solve a range of problems in everyday situations. Building on a sound mastery of numeracy, the emphasis is on process and activity, as well as knowledge. Mathematical competence involves, to different degrees, the ability and willingness to use mathematical modes of thought (logical and spatial thinking) and presentation (formulas, models, constructs, graphs, charts) (Figel, 2007).

Competence in science refers to the ability and willingness to use the body of knowledge and methodology employed to explain the natural world, in order to identify questions and to draw evidence-based conclusions. Competence in technology

is viewed as the application of that knowledge and methodology in response to perceived human wants or needs. Competence in science and technology involves an understanding of the changes caused by human activity and responsibility as an individual citizen (Figel, 2007).

Digital competence Digital competence involves the confident and critical use of Information Society Technology (IST) for work, leisure and communication. It is underpinned by basic skills in ICT: the use of computers to retrieve, assess, store, produce, present and exchange information, and to communicate and participate in collaborative networks via the Internet (Figel, 2007).

Learning to learn Learning to learn is the ability to pursue and persist in learning, to organize one's own learning, including through effective management of time and information, both individually and in groups. This competence includes awareness of one's learning process and needs, identifying available opportunities, and the ability to overcome obstacles in order to learn successfully. This competence means gaining, processing and assimilating new knowledge and skills as well as seeking and making use of guidance. Learning to learn engages learners to build on prior learning and life experiences in order to use and apply knowledge and skills in a variety of contexts: at home, at work, in education and training. Motivation and confidence are crucial to an individual's competence (Figel, 2007).

Social and civic competences These include personal, interpersonal and intercultural competence and cover all forms of behavior that equip individuals to participate in an effective and constructive way in social and working life, and particularly in increasingly diverse societies, and to resolve conflict where necessary. Civic competence equips individuals to fully participate in civic life, based on knowledge of social and political concepts and structures and a commitment to active and democratic participation (Figel, 2007).

Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship refers to an individual's ability to turn ideas into action. It includes creativity, innovation and risk-taking, as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives. This supports individuals, not only in their everyday lives at home and in society, but also in the workplace in being aware of the context of their work and being able to seize opportunities, and is a foundation for more specific skills and knowledge needed by those establishing or contributing to social or commercial activity. This should include awareness of ethical values and promote good governance (Figel, 2007).

Cultural awareness and expression Appreciation of the importance of the creative expression of ideas, experiences and emotions in a range of media, including music, performing arts, literature, and the visual arts (Figel, 2007).

As in French, competence can be broken down into three components: savoir: knowledge [such as knowing about different phases in conflict] savoir faire: knowing how to do [such as knowing how to communicate in different situations] savoir être: knowing how to be [such as empathy] (Taylor, 2007: 19).

Competence is the combined result of values, skills, attitudes and knowledge and experience. Values are the behavioral responses or actions according to the moral beliefs held by an individual or an organization. Skills are the abilities that enable you to do something. What you have in your mind that comes out of your hands. Attitudes are about thinking something, this thinking makes us feel something and we react accordingly. Knowledge is about information and understanding is about the ability to manipulate and apply knowledge. Another way to describe competence is that it is the result of knowing, doing and being. Bowyer, et all, (2000: 27).

In this context learning to learn is a quintessential tool for lifelong learning and thus education and training needs to provide the learning environment for the development of this competence for all citizens, including persons with fewer opportunities (those with special needs and school dropouts), throughout the whole lifespan (including pre-school and adult learners) and through different learning environments (formal, non-formal and informal) (Fredriksson & Hoskins, 2007).

Looking at the development of young people with fewer opportunities from a biographical perspective allows us to analyze the factors that lead to social inequality and social exclusion during the transition from childhood to adult life. On the one hand, there are structural resources and a lack of opportunities for young people in disadvantaged urban areas which frame the transition: a lack of support in education, no or few leisure time activities, a high rate of unemployment etc. On the other hand, there are also individual elements of disadvantage like a lack of competencies, wrong choices, lack of motivation or bad luck. In order to understand situations of disadvantage, we need to analyze both the individual and the structural elements which shape young people's development and may lead to school problems, lack of qualifications, no access to training, study or jobs (Alban & Geudens, 2008: 2012: 87).

“Young people with fewer opportunities” is a term which includes youngsters from many different backgrounds who, for a variety of reasons, face some form of exclusion in their lives. In certain contexts, situations or specific obstacles can prevent such young people from having access to education, to mobility, to participation, to political representation, to active citizenship, to empowerment and to inclusion in society at

large. For example, some young people may live in isolated regions or in economically disadvantaged areas where they have limited access to education. Young people with a physical or mental disability may have specific needs which cannot always be provided for. Youngsters from minority ethnic or religious backgrounds may face racism and discrimination which blocks their access to facilities, institutions or programmes. Others, like early school leavers or those with emotional or social problems, may not have the maturity or social skills necessary to cope with living on their own or holding a steady job (Schroeder, Hendriks & Bergstein: 2012: 11).

The term “*young people with fewer opportunities*” refers to the obstacles to participation and is not intended to stigmatizes this group. These obstacles can be of a socio-economic, cultural or geographical nature or may be the result of a physical or mental disability Croft, et all (2003: 7).

Inclusion, as a term, or concept, encompasses a broad range of experiences and opportunities that help create, for young people, a sense of belonging, a sense of citizenship, a sense of identity. About more than having access to employment, education and a decent (economic) standard of living it is about breaking down the barriers to social opportunities constructed by low income, discrimination, fear of the unknown and a lack of access to relevant learning experiences. Pacheco et all (2009: 6).

The following situations often prevent young people from taking part in employment, formal and non-formal education, trans-national mobility, democratic process and society at large:

1. Disability (i.e. participants with special needs): young people with mental (intellectual, cognitive, learning), physical, sensory or other disabilities etc.
2. Health problems: young people with chronic health problems, severe illnesses or psychiatric conditions etc.
3. Educational difficulties: young people with learning difficulties, early school leavers, lower qualified persons, young people with poor school performance etc.
4. Cultural differences: immigrants, refugees or descendants from immigrant or refugee families, young people belonging to a national or ethnic minority, young people with linguistic adaptation and cultural inclusion difficulties etc.
5. Economic obstacles: young people with a low standard of living, low income, dependence on social welfare system, young people in long-term unemployment or poverty, young people who are homeless, in debt or with financial problems etc.
6. Social obstacles: young people facing discrimination because of gender, age, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, disability, etc., young people with limited

social skills or anti-social or high-risk behaviors, young people in a precarious situation, (ex-)offenders, (ex-)drug or alcohol abusers, young and/or single parents, orphans etc.

7. Geographical obstacles: young people from remote or rural areas, young people living on small islands or in peripheral regions, young people from urban problem zones, young people from less serviced areas (limited public transport, poor facilities) etc.

This definition deliberately focuses on the situation young people are in, to avoid stigmatization and blame. This list is not exhaustive, but gives an indication of the type of exclusion situations we are talking about. Some target groups of this strategy, such as notably young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs), find themselves in several of the situations listed above at the same time (EC, 2014: 7).

Inclusion in the youth in action programme one of the priorities in the European Commission's new Youth in Action programme (2007-2013) is the inclusion of young people with fewer opportunities. An Inclusion Strategy has been designed as the common framework to support the efforts and Actions which the Commission, Member States, National and Executive Agencies and other organizations undertake to make inclusion a priority in their work. This "Inclusion Strategy" is based on two converging aims:

1. To Ensure the accessibility of the Youth in Action programme for young people with fewer opportunities (both those organized in youth organizations, youth councils, etc, as well as those not formally organized);
2. To stimulate the use of the Youth in Action programme as a tool to enhance the social inclusion, active citizenship and employability of young people with fewer opportunities and to contribute to social cohesion at large (EC, 2014: 11).

Specifically, the Inclusion Strategy aims to:

- Ensure a common vision and commitment among the different actors of the programme in defining the target group and implementing the strategy;
- Make it easier for youth workers working with young people with fewer opportunities to develop and implement inclusion projects with the Youth in Action programme;
- Support the quality and quantity of the projects involving young people with fewer opportunities and to maximize their impact;
- Promote the use of the Youth in Action programme as an opportunity for self-development and learning for young people with fewer opportunities and as a possible stepping stone in their personal pathway;

- To diversity and to counter mechanisms of exclusion and discrimination (EC, 2014: 12).

Easy and particularly useful project formats several project formats are relatively accessible for first-timers and inclusion groups. Listed below are examples that are useful to know about and can inspire both newcomers and experienced users of the programme to consider inclusion and diversity oriented projects:

1. Youth Exchanges offer an international mobility experience in the safety of a group and only need one partner organisation to do so. The rather short duration makes the involvement of young people with fewer opportunities appropriate. As a short term learning experience, a youth exchange can also be a good setting for discussing and learning about inclusion and diversity issues. □ European Voluntary Service (EVS) normally lasts from 2 to 12 months, but for EVS activities involving young people with fewer opportunities (and group EVS) it is allowed to go for a shorter period, starting from two weeks.

2. Transnational Youth Initiatives, in the context of a Strategic Partnership, allow informal groups of young people in minimum two countries to address challenges encountered in their communities – the project can be set up and managed by the young people themselves. Erasmus+ also has a number of project types in the field of Youth that allow youth workers to improve their skills and competence in inclusion and diversity. On a wider scale, there are also project formats available that aim to support new partnerships and impact practice and policy in the youth field:

1. Training and networking allows youth workers/youth leaders to exchange and gain professional competences to work on inclusion and diversity.

2. Strategic Partnerships is a novel format introduced under Erasmus+ aiming to support projects that develop innovative practices and ideas. Stakeholders, such as youth organizations, experts in relevant sectors (health, justice, employment etc.), education institutions and many more can join forces to address and find solutions to the situations faced by young people with fewer opportunities. Structured Dialogue allows organizations to set up national or international meetings to interact with policy makers, get the voice of young people with fewer opportunities heard, and/or target the topic of inclusion. Additional support Young people with fewer opportunities often just need a little more support to make the transition to an international project.

There are several funding options available under Erasmus+ for this purpose. Advance Planning Visit:

1. These planning visits help to build trust, understanding and a solid partnership between organizations. Young people can be involved in this visit to integrate them fully in the project design.

2. Additional group leaders: The programme guide indicates a minimum of group leaders per national group, but no maximum. It is possible to take more leaders than the minimum for an inclusion and diversity project. The application procedures allow applicants to combine several activities (Youth Exchanges, EVS, and training courses) strategically within one application.

3. Mentorship: It may be a good idea to consider whether young participants with fewer opportunities would benefit from the support of a mentor; for instance reinforced mentorship in European Voluntary Service.

4. Recognition: Every participant in an Erasmus+ project in the field of Youth is entitled to a Youthpass. This is more than just a certificate. Youth workers can use Youthpass to help young people reflect on their learning and train them in how to present the competences they have gained. These skills, in addition to the certificate itself, can be of particular help for young people with fewer opportunities such as NEETs who are trying to get a job. Linguistic Support: Organizations can apply for additional funding or access to online support for linguistic training in long term youth mobility (lasting more than 2 months) (EC, 2014: 9-10).

Enlargement of competence:

The learning is about...

- their cultural identity,
- knowledge of other cultures and specific subjects,
- organizing things together,
- perception of others,
- dealing with conflicts while trying to understand each
- other or having different concepts,
- a lot of small things concerning independence, democracy, living together in a group, expressing themselves, dealing with unforeseen situations
- a lot more! (Bergstein, 2006: 26).

While the new EU Youth Strategy addresses all young people, it stresses that special attention should be given to youth with fewer opportunities. The Strategy operates with eight 'fields of action', which are all important elements of social cohesion policy: Employment & Entrepreneurship, Education & Training, Social Inclusion, Health & Well-being, Participation, Culture & Creativity, Volunteering and Youth & the World. One particular achievement of the new EU Youth Strategy, adopted for the period 2010 to 2018, is its strong emphasis on the transversal and cross-sectoral nature of youth policy (Mairesse, 2010: 8-9).

The European Commission's Youth in Action programme for the years 2007 – 2013 is an important instrument for supporting the poverty transmits between

generations. Children raised in families experiencing long-term poverty are less likely to complete higher education and more prone to take on lower paid jobs or experience unemployment. It is therefore particularly important to develop comprehensive and transversal policy responses for young people that connect the different policy fields of education and employment, social inclusion, health, participation and young people's well-being. The European Union is responding to this challenge and in the last decade the youth dimension of EU's policies and actions have become more clearly articulated (Mairesse, 2010: 8).

EU Youth Strategy and for promoting social cohesion in Europe. The programme offers opportunities for young people to take part in youth initiatives and cross-border exchanges as well as voluntary projects outside the formal education system. With its focus on non-formal learning, and reaching out to young people with fewer opportunities as one of its permanent priorities, the Youth in Action programme reaches out to young people who may have quit school early or come from a family background with limited resources. In this way, it is an important Commission instrument to empower all young people, in particular those with fewer opportunities (Mairesse, 2010: 9). In between the seminars, participants are provided with a range of support measures to help them overcome challenges and develop competences (Bajja, 2010: 29).

Honey, Peter and Mumford, Alan (1992) developed Kolb (1984)'s experiential learning circle, here transformed into a spiral to stress continual development. According to this theory, what is important is not what happens to you, but what you do with what happens to you. Experiential learning is seen as a 4 step process. It does not matter how long it takes, the most important is to go from the experience phase to the thinking it over, to the critical analysis and generalization to come to planning of the use of the newly acquired competence.

- Stage 1 – Doing and experiencing is part of everyday life but it can also be an arranged opportunity.
- Stage 2 – Observing and reflecting on what has happened to you.
- Stage 3 – Concluding from the experience and generalizing.
- Stage 4 – Applying the newly acquired competence or planning a new experience.

Whatever terms we use, we should acknowledge that:

- words are powerful and complex and are quite capable of giving offence – even when the thinking behind them was well intentioned and no harm or disrespect was meant by the speaker;

- words shape the way that we think and respond. Descriptive terms, such as “young offender” or “victim of abuse”, for example, often have associations which are not proven or justified but can be hard to shake off, once used;
- and although words are important, we need not get too obsessed with them. If we spend too much time worrying about words we might not get anything useful done. Croft, et all (2003: 13).

The definition speaks about persistent poverty but it could just as easily describe long-term exclusion. The reality it points to is the reality facing many marginalized young people in our societies. It highlights three important aspects of people’s situations:

- Multiple insecurities – The most vulnerable young people are often facing a number of different insecurities in their lives at the same time, for example: unemployment, discrimination and isolation; or inadequate housing, health problems and inconsistent education and training.
- Persistence – If such multiple insecurities endure over the long-term they can build up and compound one another, for example: inadequate housing can lead to poor health; discrimination can lead to unemployment or problems at school; family break up to isolation.
- Erosion of rights and responsibilities – Eventually people’s basic social, economic, cultural, civil and political rights and responsibilities are undermined or under threat wholesale: it is difficult to succeed at school if you face discrimination on a daily basis.

Without a basic education, how will you find a decent job? Without a decent job how will you afford adequate housing? When your confidence is shattered and people do not understand your situation it is very difficult to join in cultural or civil activities. All these pressures can put intolerable strain on family life. This sort of vicious circle can go round and round, in the end affecting every part of a person’s life. Croft, et all (2003: 15).

Step one: Go out to the places where you can contact the young persons you are targeting. Get to know their environment and life situation (see 4.1: Young people in their communities). Talk informally to the young people about their needs and wishes, and do not forget to gather information as well about the “invisible” young people (those you do not meet on the streets). Listen actively but do not promise things you cannot deliver. Avoid being patronizing.

Step two: It is important to build trust between the young people and yourself (see 6.3: Building trust). It is important not to be judgmental or to preach to people when they tell you about past experiences. Show interest in what they are doing, have

done and plan to do. Here you can sow the seeds for future participation of the young people in your activities.

Step three: Analyze the information you gather from your contacts with the target group. Check what challenges they face in daily life, what obstacles they are facing in joining in youth activities, what they like and dislike, and so on. This information should give you an idea what types of activities or projects the young people would like, and which would be not appropriate.

Step four: When you then decide to set up projects geared towards the target group, use all the information you gathered and involve the young persons in it from the start, throughout the project or in all activities. Although improvisation skills and flexibility are vital to a project, it is important – especially when dealing with vulnerable young people – to have a plan. This helps to keep your aims and objectives clear and gives you guidelines for your work with the young people. Be transparent in what you are trying to reach – and make sure there is something in it for the young people. More information on setting up a project can be found in the T-Kit on Project Management. Croft, et al (2003: 18). *reach young people with fewer opportunities through a variety of methods which are flexible and quickly adaptable. (EC, 2010: 4).

Young people should make the best of their potential. This vision is addressed to all, but actions should focus on those with fewer opportunities. It is based on a dual approach: – Investing in Youth: putting in place greater resources to develop policy areas that affect young people in their daily life and improve their wellbeing. – Empowering Youth: promoting the potential of young people for the renewal of society and to contribute to EU values and goals (EC, 2009: 4)

Competence is often used interchangeably with the term skill, but they do not really mean the same thing. Competence means the ability to apply knowledge, know-how and skills in a stable/recurring or changing situation. Two elements are crucial: applying what one knows and can do to a specific task or problem, and being able to transfer this ability between different situations (Bowyer & Geudens, 2005: 42)

They should be encouraged to reflect, describe, analyze and communicate what they experience during the activities in which they participate (Vink, 1999). Schools can supply a youth worker with basic information about the neighborhood, from the number of young persons at the school to the cultural structure, the number of school leavers and the level of education. But you might also consider co-operating with teachers or even employers when setting up non-formal education programmes. An additional advantage of this is that it could be possible to use equipment and space available in the school. A disadvantage, however, might be that the young people are

already averse to school and unwilling to spend more time there, so careful preparation and deliberation is necessary.

The formal education system (schools, universities, vocational training) aims at providing young people a basic knowledge to be used for their social integration into society. Unfortunately, in many cases, the formal education system fails to provide all young people with their learning needs due to various reasons. Therefore, other sources of personal developments should be available. Non-formal education may be one of them, especially – but not solely – for young people with fewer opportunities (Strenner, 2006). In this vain the problem statement of this study is what are the volunteer leaders ideas on competence, fever opportunity and enlargement competence of fever opportunity.

4. Method

Overall, this study is designed as qualitative. 32 European volunteer youth leaders participated in the study. This group met in Belgium in Antwerp with an educational workshop arranged by SALTO-YOUTH in 2011. The qualitative data gathering techniques such as document analysis and interview was used in this study. Documents related to competence, fever opportunities and non-formal education published by European Council were examined deeply. Three interview questions developed.

These questions are:

- Please could you explain what it means competence?
- Please could you explain what it means fever opportunity?
- Please say about your ideas on how develop competence of fever opportunities?

32 European youth volunteer leaders explained their ideas. All interviews were recorded. The voice records were transcribed. 48 Times new roman 12 type size pages gathered. These pages were coded. There are 92% code reconciliation is enough for reliability (Miles & Huberman, 1994). A qualitative research has been carried out. After interviews, (the leaders were asked about their ideas and thoughts) with 32 students, transcript pages were gathered after ten sessions of drama. Qualitative research recognizes a complex and dynamic social word. It involves researchers' active engagement with participants and acknowledges that understanding is construed and multiple realities exist (Tindall, 2002). Table I illustrates participant ideas on the topic.

It is openly seen from Table I that participants the youth leaders have knowledge about what is competence and what is it means fever opportunity. This is parallel with the related references. EU, 2006; Pacheco, et all 2009; Alban & Geudens, 2008: 2012;

Schroeder, Hendriks & Bergstein; 2012; Schild & Hebel, 2006 express the competence in eight items. These are:

- 1) Communication in the mother tongue;
- 2) Communication in foreign languages;
- 3) Mathematical competence and basic competences in science and technology;
- 4) Digital competence;
- 5) Learning to learn;
- 6) Social and civic competences;
- 7) Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship; and
- 8) Cultural awareness and expression.

Participants of the study the leaders have enough information about competence. From 100% to 81.25% they have knowledge on what competence is. Competences are defined here as a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes appropriate to the context. Key competences are those which all individuals need for personal fulfillment and development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employment.

93.25% is the participants of study knowledge on what is fewer opportunities. The term "*young people with fewer opportunities*" refers to the obstacles to participation and is not intended to stigmatise this group. These obstacles can be of a socio-economic, cultural or geographical nature or may be the result of a physical or mental disability. Croft, et all (2003). 7 "*Young people with fewer opportunities*" is a term which includes youngsters from many different backgrounds who, for a variety of reasons, face some form of exclusion in their lives. In certain contexts, situations or specific obstacles can prevent such young people from having access to education, to mobility, to participation, to political representation, to active citizenship, to empowerment and to inclusion in society at large.

5. Data analysis and reliability

The two terms are sine qua non for all researches not only quantitative but also qualitative ones. Reliability: a term used in quantitative research to indicate the consistency of measurement. The term is also applied to some qualitative research, particularly that which adopts a realist epistemology. In qualitative research, the evaluative criteria that are applied are more commonly transparency and trustworthiness. Validity: the extent to which research measures or reflects what it claims to. Most meaningfully used in research with a realist epistemology Forest, 2011: 108).

The thematic model can be applied to a wide range of narrative text, including narratives produced in interviews and written documents. The analyst can start the thematic analysis by the open coding of data. The steps in the categorical content analysis described by Lieblich et al. (1998) can be used in the process of thematic analysis. The categorical content analysis focuses on thematic similarities and differences between narratives generated in interviews. The analytical approach of Lieblich et al. (1998: 112–113) involves breaking the text into smaller units of content.

Forest (2011) states four steps of application of thematic model:

1. Selection of the subtext/segments
2. Definition of thematic categories
3. Sorting the material into categories
4. Drawing conclusions (Forest, 2011: 108)

Therefore, reliability, validity and triangulation, if they are to be relevant research concepts, particularly from a qualitative point of view, have to be redefined as we have seen in order to reflect the multiple ways of establishing truth (Golafshani, 2003: 604). Written data of individual interviews coded by three specialists. All specialists have PhD in education.

6. Results

Table I illustrates themes, samples, frequencies and percentages of over all the study. There were 32 youth leaders that participated in the study.

Table I: Themes, Samples, Frequencies and Percentages

Theme	Sample	Frequency	Percentage
Competence			
Mother tongue	They should know their own language	28	87.50
Foreign language	They have to capable of one of any European language especial where they live	30	93.75
Mathematic	It is had better good at in math.	28	87.50
Digital,	Digital competence is important.	26	81.25
Learning	They should capable of learning of learning.	30	93,75
Social	Getting along with others is crucial.	32	100
Entrepreneurship	Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship one of required competence	30	93.75
Cultural	Awareness of culture is important	28	87.50
Fever Opportunity	Fever opportunity is stand for missing chance of education, good health occasion due to living in faraway or some disasters.	30	93.75

Development Competence of Fever Opportunity	Governments should supply	5	15.62
---	---------------------------	---	-------

7. Discussion and Conclusions

All participants expressed their idea on competence, fever opportunity and enlargement competence of fever opportunity. Competence has broad meaning of the quality of being competent; adequacy; possession of required skill, knowledge, qualification, or capacity. In human resources, it means a standardized requirement for an individual to properly perform a specific job.

The Reference Framework sets out eight key competences:

1. Communication in the mother tongue;
2. Communication in foreign languages;
3. Mathematical competence and basic competences in science and technology;
4. Digital competence;
5. Learning to learn;
6. Social and civic competences;
7. Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship; and
8. Cultural awareness and expression. (EU, 2006: 13; Pacheco, et al 2009: 60; Alban & Geudens, 2008: 2012: 83; Schroeder, Hendriks & Bergstein:, 2012: 19; Schild & Hebel, 2006: 9).

32 youth volunteer leaders expressed their ideas in competence in same manner. Young people with fewer opportunities are young people that are at a disadvantage compared to their peers because they face one or more of the situations and obstacles mentioned in the non-exhaustive list below. In certain contexts, these situations or obstacles prevent young people from having effective access to formal and non-formal education, transnational mobility and participation, active citizenship, empowerment and inclusion in society at large (SALTO, 2016). In this study working group the participants expressed their ideas in same way. But it should be beer in mind that fever opportunities is a big concept. There are some branches of it:

Social obstacles: young people facing discrimination because of gender, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, disability, etc.- young people with limited social skills or anti-social or risky sexual behaviors- young people in a precarious situation- (ex)offenders, (ex)drug or alcohol abusers- young and/or single parents; orphans- young people from broken families

Economic obstacles: young people with a low standard of living, low income, dependence on social welfare system- in long-term unemployment or poverty- young people who are homeless, young people in debt or with financial problems.

Disability: mental (intellectual, cognitive, learning)- physical, sensory- other disabilities

Educational difficulties: young people with learning difficulties- early school-leavers and school dropouts- lower qualified persons- young people with poor school performance

Cultural differences: young immigrants or refugees, or descendants from immigrant or refugee families- young people belonging to a national or ethnic minority- young people with linguistic adaptation and cultural inclusion problems

Health problems: young people with chronic health problems, severe illnesses or psychiatric conditions- young people with mental health problems

Geographical obstacles: young people from remote or rural areas- young people living on small islands or peripheral regions- young people from urban problem zones- young people from less serviced areas (limited public transport, poor facilities, abandoned villages)

Non formal education is seem to be key answer for development of competence in fever opportunity youths Schild & Hebel, 2006; E.U., 2015). It is pity that the working group has limited knowledge about this issue. Youth volunteer leaders and their students should be participate educational activities arranged by organizations such as SALTO-YOUTH. These activities have been conducting by very competent teachers trainers. Non formal education is important issue for development of competence in fever opportunities. Later studies should be arranged about dimensions and intensity of educational programs of European Union organizations. Investigating of new competence types especially today's world mobile structure do to the illegal immigrations from east to Europe.

References

1. Alban, K. & Geudens, T. (2012). *Youth and the City*. Brussel: SALTO.
2. Bajja, N. L. (2010). ENTER! A 2-year project on the access to social rights for young people from disadvantaged neighborhoods *Coyote*, 15, 28, 30.
3. Bergstein, R. (2006). The European strategy on recognition of non-formal learning in the YOUTH programme. *Coyote*, 11, 26-28.

4. Bowyer, J. (2000). Managing your personal resources. *Organizational Management T-kit*. Strasbourg: Council of Europe publishing
5. Bowyer, J., Geudens, T. (2005). *Promoting Recognition of Youth Work across Europe*. Brussels: SALTO.
6. Croft, et all (2003). T-Kit on Social Inclusion Strasbourg: Council of Europe publishing
7. EC, (2009). An EU Strategy for Youth – Investing and Empowering A renewed open method of coordination to address youth challenges and opportunities. COM.
8. EC, 2010 COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the member states, meeting within the Council, on youth work 3046th EDUCATION, YOUTH, CULTURE and SPORT Council meeting Brussels, 18 and 19 November 2010
9. European Commission (2014). Erasmus+ Inclusion and Diversity Strategy–in the field of Youth
10. Eurydice (2002) Key competencies: A developing concept in general compulsory education. Brussels: Eurydice/European Commission.
11. Figel, J.(2007). *The Key Competences for Lifelong Learning*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
12. Fredriksson, U. and Hoskins, B. (2007). The development of learning to learn in a European context. *Curriculum Journal* Vol. 18, No.2, pp. 127 - 134.
13. Frost, N. (2011). *Qualitative research methods in psychology: combining core approaches*. Open University Press.
14. Golafshani, N. (2003). Understanding Reliability and Validity in Qualitative Research. *The Qualitative Report*, 8 (4), 597-606.
15. Honey, Peter and Mumford, Alan (1992). *The Manual of Learning Styles*, 7-0. Adapted version.
16. Hoskins, B. & Fredriksson, U. (2008). *Learning to Learn: What is it and can it be measured?* Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities
17. Kolb, David (1984) *Experiential learning*, Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall
18. Lieblich, A., Tuval-Mashiach, R. & Zilber, T. (1998). *Narrative Research: Reading, Analysis and Interpretation*. London: Sage Publications.
19. Mairesse, P. (2010). Social Cohesion at the Heart of EU Policy. *Coyote*, 15, 7-11.
20. Miles, M. B. & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis* (2nd edition). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications

21. Pacheco, A. A., Gherga, E., Tammi, L. & Geudens, T. (2009). *Going International - Inclusion for All* (updated 2009) – practical methods and advice for youth workers organising their first international project for young people with fewer opportunities Brussel: SALTO.
22. Rychen, D.S. (2004) Key competencies for all: an overarching conceptual frame of reference. In Rychen, D. S. and Tiana, A. (Eds) *Developing Key Competencies in Education: Some lessons from International and National Experience*. Geneva: UNESCO / International Bureau of Education
23. SALTO-YOUTH NET. (2016, September 10) Retrieved from <https://www.salto-youth.net/tools/otlas-partner-finding/help/young-people-with-fewer-opportunities/> (Retrewee
24. Schild, H. J. & Hebel, M.(2006). Milestones for formal and social recognition of non-formal and informal learning in youth work. *Coyote*. 11, 8-12.
25. Schroeder, K., Hendriks, A. & Bergstein, R. (2012). Youth Pass for all. *Recognition of Learning, Focusing on Inclusion Groups*. Brussel: SALTO.
26. Strenner,S.(2006). Bring more peace into non-formal education. Peace and violencein non-learning groups. *Coyote*, 11.
27. Taylor,M. (2007). *European Portfolio for youth leaders and youth workers*. Strasbourg: Directorate of Youth and Sport
28. Tindal, C. (2002). *Issues of Evaluation 142-160 Qualitative Methods in Psychology A Research Guide* (Edt. Banister, et al.) London: Open University Press.
29. Vink, Caroline (1999). "Giving credit: certification and assessment of non-formal education *Coyte* Issue 1, Strasbourg: Council of Europe and European Commission.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).